

Original Article

Clinical Profile of Hospitalized Children with Febrile Convulsion: A Study of 179 Cases

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Abstract

Febrile Convulsion is the common febrile seizure which affects usually the children between the ages of five months to six years of age. This study was conducted to look into the clinical profile of 179 cases of hospitalized febrile convulsion Patients admitted in ICMH from January 2004 to November 2005. There were 126 (70.3 %) male and 53 (29.6%) female cases. Most of the children (56.9 %) belonged to the age group of 1-3 years, followed by 6-12 months (30.7%) . All the cases had generalized seizure. The attack was first febrile convulsion in 149 (83.2%) cases. There was single episode of seizure in 118(65.9%). Two episodes in 38(21.2%) and more than two episodes of seizure in 23 (12.8%) cases. Duration of seizure was mostly less than 15 minutes in 141 (78.7%) cases. The associated illness with febrile convulsion were URTI (48.4%), pneumonia (27%), diarrhoea(18.8%), measles(1.8%)and UTI (1.2%). No children had residual paralysis. Eighty six percent children were discharged with advice against 10% discharged on risk bond. Conclusion: Children between 1-3 years were found vulnerable to febrile convulsion with male preponderance. The associated extra cranial infection found were URTI, Pneumonia and Diarrhoea. The main risk of recurrence was family history of febrile convulsion and family history of epilepsy.

Introduction:

A febrile convulsion is defined as seizure occurring in a child aged six months to five years (in the age group of one to six years have at least one episode of febrile convulsion.^{1,2}) precipitated by fever arising from infection outside the nervous system³. The direct cause of a febrile seizure is not certain; however, it is normally precipitated by a recent upper respiratory infection or gastroenteritis. A febrile seizure is the effect of a sudden rise in temperature, 102.0°F or higher, rather than a fever that has been present for a prolonged length of time.⁴

Fever is the single most chief complaint in 40–50% of children⁵. Febrile convulsions occur in 2–4% of children under the age of five years and these are the commonest cause of convulsions under five years of age^{6,7}. Simple febrile convulsions last for less than 15 minutes, are generalized, and do not

recur in 24 hour period. Focal, multiple and prolonged febrile convulsions are labelled as complex⁸. Febrile seizures are slightly more common in boys⁹. There is a positive family history of febrile convulsions in up to 30% of cases³. The median age of occurrence is 18-22 months⁹.

The objective of the study was to see the clinical profile of hospitalized children with febrile convulsion.

Materials and Methods:

This study was carried out in Paediatrics department of Institute of Child and Mother Health, Dhaka. The study included 179 children of ages five months to six years, who were sequentially admitted in Paediatrics department with diagnosis of febrile convulsions. Children with meningitis, encephalitis, developmentally abnormal children and children below five months or above six years of age were excluded from the study. All information about patients was collected retrospectively from January' 2004 to

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November'2005 from patients file & was recorded in preformed questionnaire. History including family history, nature, duration and type of convulsion; previous history of convulsion with or without fever were also recorded. Convulsions were labelled as febrile mainly by process of exclusion of other causes and on the basis of history, clinical examination and relevant laboratory investigations.

In this study lumbar puncture was not done as a routine investigation and it was performed on clinical suspicion of meningitis^{10,4}. Irritability, bulging fontanel, neck stiffness, positive Kerning's sign, drowsiness, prolonged focal seizure, multiple

seizures, petechial rash were considered signs of meningitis and lumbar puncture was performed¹¹.

Results:

Table-I shows sociodemographic factors and clinical profile of febrile convulsion patients.

Out of 179 patients with febrile convulsion who were admitted at ICMH, 126 (70.4%) male and 53 (29.6%) female. Febrile convulsion occurred in 102 patients (57%) between 1yr to 3 yrs of age, 7 patients (3.9%) at the age of less than 6 months, 55 (30.7%) at the age from 6 months to 1 yr, 10 (5.6%) patients at the from 3yrs to 5yrs of age, 2 (1.2%)

Table-I
Socio-demographic Factors of Febrile convulsion (N=179)

		No. of Pts (N=179)	%
Sex	Male	126	70.4
	Female	53	29.6
Age Range	<6mons	7	3.9
	6mons-1yr	55	30.7
	1yr-3yrs	102	57
	3yrs-5yrs	10	5.6
	5yrs-6yrs	2	1.2
	>6yrs	3	1.6
Family history	Present	14	7.8
	Absent	165	92.2
Types of seizure	Focal seizure	0	0
	Generalized seizure	179	100
No. of seizure	Single seizure episode	118	66
	Two seizure episodes	38	21.2
	More than two seizure episodes	23	12.8
Duration of seizure	<15mins	141	78.8
	15mins-30mins	17	9.5
	>30mins	21	11.7
History of previous convulsion	Present	30	16.8
	Absent	149	83.2
Onset of seizure	Within 12 hrs	8	4.7
	Within 12-24 hrs	73	42.7
	Within >24 hrs	90	52.6
Associated illness	Otitis media	4	2.5
	URTI	77	48.4
	Pneumonia	43	27.0
	Diarrhoea	30	18.9
	Urinary tract infection	2	1.2
	Measles	3	1.9

Table-II
Recurrence and outcome of febrile convulsion (N=179):

	Risk	No. of Pts (N=179)	%
Factors of Recurrence of febrile convulsion (N=30)	Family history of febrile convulsion	10	33.3
	Family history of epilepsy	9	30
	Atypical convulsion	3	10
	High temperature at admission	4	13.3
	Sex		
	Male	20	66.6
	Female	10	33.3
Outcome of febrile convulsion	Discharge with advice (D/A)	154	86.6
	Discharge on request (DOR)	7	3.9
	Discharge on risk bond (DORB)	18	10.0
	Expired	0	0
	Residual paralysis		
	Present	0	0
	Absent	179	100

patients from 5yrs to 6yrs of age and 3 (1.6%) patients at the age of more than 6yrs. 165 (92.2%) pts had no family history of febrile convulsion and 14 (7.8%) had positive family history. 179 (100%) patients had generalized seizure. 118 (65.9%) patients had single episode of seizure, 38 (21.2%) patients had two episodes of seizure and 23 (12.8%) pts had more than two episodes of seizure. Seizures persisted less than 15 minutes in 141 (78.8%) patients, 15mins to 30mins in 17 (9.5%) patients and in 21 (11.7%) patients seizures persisted more than 30mins. 149 (83.2%) patients had no history of previous convulsion and 30 (16.8%) had history previous of convulsion. Out of 171 patients 90 (52.6%) patients had developed seizure after 24hrs of febrile episode, 73 (42.7%) had developed seizure within 12-24hrs and 8 (4.7%) had developed seizure within 12hrs after fever. Among the 179 patients the associated illness with febrile convulsion were otitis media 4 cases (2.5%), upper respiratory tract infection (URTI) 77 cases (48.4%), pneumonia 43 cases (27.0%), diarrhoea 30 cases (18.9%), urinary tract infection (UTI) 2 cases (1.2%) and 3 cases (1.9%) were measles.

Table-2 shows recurrence and outcome of febrile convulsion patients.

In 30 patients presenting with recurrent febrile convulsion 10 (33.3%) patients had positive family history, 9(30%) patients had family history of

epilepsy, 3 (10%) patients had atypical convulsion and 4 (13.3%) had high temperature at admission. In those 30 patients; 20 (66.6%) patients were male and 10 (33.3%) patients were female. Out of 179 (100%), no patient had developed residual paralysis due to febrile convulsion. Out of 179 (100%), no death occurred following febrile convulsion.

Discussion:

The purpose of this study was to establish the age, sex distribution, clinical presentations, risk factors and the immediate outcome of Febrile Convulsion. The etiology of Febrile Convulsion was based on history, clinical findings and diagnostic investigations. Febrile convulsions occur in 2-4% of children between the ages of 6 months and 5 years and these are the commonest cause of convulsions under five years of age^{6,7}. Simple febrile convulsions last for less than 15 minutes, are generalized, and do not recur in 24 hours period. Focal, multiple and prolonged febrile convulsions are known as complex seizures⁸. Febrile seizures are slightly more common in boys than girls⁹, In this study 70.4 percent were male and 29.6 percent were female. In other studies it has been seen that febrile seizures occur more frequently in males than in females and the reason is unknown.^{12,13}

Febrile seizures starting in first year of life peak in second year and the incidence declines with increasing age¹⁴. In present study 3.9 percent of

children had febrile convulsion below 6 months, 34.6 percent below 12 months, 91.6 percent below 36 months, 98.4 percent below 6yrs. These findings correlate with study conducted by Tahir Saeed Siddiqui¹⁵ where 44 percent of children had febrile convulsion below 12 months, 77 percent below 24 months and 87 percent below 36 months. In another study¹⁶ it was seen that 39.5 percent of cases were below 12 months and 60.5 percent of cases were more than 12 months. In a study by Wallace in 1975¹⁷, 37 percent of children were below 16 months and 63 percent were above 16 months.

If initial febrile convulsion is complex (i.e. focal features, duration more than 15 minutes, repeated within the same illness) it increases the risk of recurrence as well as future afebrile seizures^{18, 19}. Many studies have reported that complex fits constitute about one third of total cases. In the present study, according to the number of seizure during the period of illness, complex fits (2 or >2 seizure) was found in 34 percent cases and simple fits 66 percent cases; according to the duration of seizure during the period of illness, complex fits (>15 mins) was seen in 21.2 percent and simple fits in 78.8 percent cases. In a study by Tahir Saeed Siddiqui^{13,15}, complex fits occurred in 35 percent of cases and simple fits in 65 percent and in another study by al-Eissa *et al* in 1992²⁰, 62 percent cases were simple and 38 percent were of complex nature. However Wallace-SJ in 1975¹⁷ has reported complex febrile convulsion in 61.8 percent of cases.

A positive family history of febrile seizures points to the importance of genetic factors and common environmental exposures. In this study 7.8 percent of the children had positive family history of febrile convulsions. Saidulhaque in 1981¹⁶ had reported 20 percent of children with positive family history in his study. Farwel in 1994²¹ reported positive family history in 29 percent of the cases. Tahir Saeed Siddiqui¹⁵ reported positive family history in 30 percent of the cases. KK Chan *et al* in a study²² in Hong Kong children found recurrent febrile convulsion in 22.6% cases and young age was the only significant factor for recurrence.

The most common cause of fever leading to febrile convulsions was upper respiratory tract infections (72 percent). Rantala *et al* in 1995²³ has also

reported in their study that upper respiratory tract infection was the most common cause of fever (67 percent) in febrile convulsions which is nearly consistent with this study where upper respiratory tract infection was found in 48.4 percent cases followed by pneumonia in 27.0 percent cases and diarrhoea 18.9 percent.

Conclusion:

Majority of febrile convulsions occurred in between 1yr to 3 years of age, there was male preponderance, the most common underlying cause of febrile convulsion was upper respiratory tract infection followed by pneumonia and diarrhoea. The main risk factor of recurrence was family history of febrile convulsion and family history of epilepsy.

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